

Religion in Greco-Roman Alexandria

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Entry tags: Egyptian Religions, Hellenistic Religions, Greek Cult, Religious Group, Roman Religious Traditions, Jewish Traditions

The aim here is to analyse the religious atmosphere of Alexandria, the city founded by Alexander on the Egyptian Mediterranean Coast in 331 BCE. The city grew as immigrants from all over the Mediterranean world settled. The population was composed as a mixture of Greeks, Egyptians, Jews and Macedonians inhabitants, therefore the cults were varied, as ancient traditions coexisted, were combined and reinvented. The new religion of Serapis was also established by the court and its syncretism can be seen as a metaphor to the cosmopolitan environment of the city.

Date Range: 300 BCE - 200 CE

Region: Alexandria, Egypt

Region tags: Africa, Egypt

Alexandria located on the Mediterranean coast of Egypt.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: FRASER, Peter M. Ptolomaic Alexandria. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1972. 3 v.
- Source 2: BOWMAN, Alan. Egypt after the Pharaohs 332 B.C. -A.D.642. California: University of California Press, 1986.
- Source 3: HARRIS, W.V.; RUFFINI, G. (Eds.). Ancient Alexandria between Egypt and Greece. Columbia Studies in the Classical Tradition. Leiden: Brill, 2004.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.loebclassics.com/>

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: Plutarch, Moralia, Isis and Osiris.
- Source 1 Description: Strabo. Geography, book 17.
- Source 2 URL: DIODORUS SICULUS, Library of History, Books 1-2.

– Source 2 Description: Flavius Josephus. Antiquities; The Jewish Wars.

– Source 3 URL: Philo. On the Embassy to Gaius.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The Jewish community had a Greek version of the Torah translated to Greek in Alexandria, the Septuagint, probably as a demand of the community that was starting to lose knowledge of the Hebrew language and was using mainly Greek. The "Letter of Aristeas", probably written during the 2nd century BC describes this episode in a legendary manner. The other religions that coexisted were not based on texts.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are they oral:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: There is a version of the translation process called "The Letter of Aristeas" produced probably during the second century BC. This version was also established and adapted by Flavius Josephus in the "Jewish Antiquities" book 12, 1-3.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Revealed by a high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Even if the settlers and the Ptolemaic court tried to emphasize traditional Greek cults since Alexandria was founded, ancient Egyptian practices were also considered and aimed towards the natives, that were a considerable part of the population of the city.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: In general, Greek, Egyptian and Jewish religious practices coexisted in Alexandria. We know of more serious conflicts between Greeks and Jews that happened during the Roman Period, mainly the conflict between Greeks and Jews that happened during 38 AD. The tensions were aggravated especially during the government of the emperor Caligula and Claudius and they were not only centred on religious matters (Josephus and Philo narrate some of these episodes).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Mainly problems between Alexandrian Greeks and the Jewish community.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: In specific occasions there were reactions of the native temples towards the Greco-Macedonian Court, but they were not specifically political in content.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: The literary sources mention many temples (devoted both to Greek and Egyptian gods) that were introduced in the city during its development by the early Ptolemies. The most important temple was the one devoted to Serapis, called the Serapeum. Other temples were also introduced during Roman conquest. Strabo (Geography, 17.10), who wrote during the early Roman empire mentions the city was full of temples, palaces and public places, and also mentions that ancient sacred places were abandoned.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: Strabo and other authors mention a temple where the tomb of Alexander was located, when Ptolemy I Soter brought the body from Babylon to the city and built a golden tomb for it. Strabo clarifies that at his time it was made of glass and that other Ptolemies also rested there (Geography, 17,1.8). It seems that the place became a landmark in the city, where many people visited, as it was constantly mentioned. Suetonius also mentions that when Octavian conquered the city, he dedicated honours to the tomb of Alexander and left many flowers (Augustus, 18).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Notes: The catacombs and necropolis in Alexandria are the most well preserved archaeological sites within the city and they mix Egyptian and Greek architectural styles. The main examples are the Chatby necropolis, Anfushi necropolis and Kom al-Chougafa.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: The better preserved temple in the city is the Serapeum, which was probably also the main temple. We know that the part of Alexandria where the palaces were located are now underwater, because of the level of the sea that has risen. Strabo mentions that the neighbourhood with palaces and important public spaces where a third of the city space, so probably many important temples were located in this area (Geography, 17.8). Arrian (also writing during roman times, and after Strabo) also says that the city was full of temples, but affirms (clearly anachronically aimed to glorify Alexander) that the places where the temples should stand (to Greek gods and to the Egyptian Isis) were all determined by Alexander.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Altars:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: Strabo (Geography, 17.10) mentions that near the Serapeum there were many sacred places that were abandoned and replaced by new constructions at his time and that ancient buildings were neglected. He adds also that the city was full of public and sacred structures, and that the most beautiful was the gymnasium, where there were courts, forests and a sanctuary to the god Pan.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: We can mention the massive lighthouse of the Pharos, where there was also probably statues of gods.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: Ptolemies esteemed Olympian gods and the new religion of Serapis and also merged them with some Greeks cult to establish the cult of the governors, while the roman conquest also brought the emperors cult to the city.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Notes: During the Roman Period Greek Alexandrians were free from the poll-tax, while Egyptians and Jews were sublet to payments. So the roman power tended to overvalue Greek culture, which in general coincided with Greek cults.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

–At home

–All public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– I don't know

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– All public spaces

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: An example is the Apis bull that was found in the Serapeum site during excavations at the end of the XIX century.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: Fragments of colossal statues of Ptolemaic kings and queens were found during the underwater findings.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Other features of iconography:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are pilgrimages present:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Even if the settlers and the Ptolemaic court tried to emphasize traditional Greek cults since Alexandria was founded, ancient Egyptian practices were also considered and aimed towards the natives, that were a considerable part of the population of the city.

Specific to this answer:

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Notes: In general, Greek, Egyptian and Jewish religious practices coexisted in Alexandria. We know of more serious conflicts between Greeks and Jews that happened during the Roman Period, mainly the conflict between Greeks and Jews that happened during 38 AD. The tensions were aggravated especially during the government of the emperor Caligula and Claudius and they were not only centred on religious matters (Josephus and Philo narrate

some of these episodes).

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Notes: Mainly problems between Alexandrian Greeks and the Jewish community.

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Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

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culture, which in general coincided with Greek cults.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The Jewish community had a Greek version of the Torah translated to Greek in Alexandria, the Septuagint, probably as a demand of the community that was starting to lose knowledge of the Hebrew language and was using mainly Greek. The "Letter of Aristeas", probably written during the 2nd century BC describes this episode in a legendary manner. The

other religions that coexisted were not based on texts.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are they oral:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: There is a version of the translation process called "The Letter of Aristeas" produced probably during the second century BC. This version was also established and adapted by Flavius Josephus in the "Jewish Antiquities" book 12, 1-3.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: The literary sources mention many temples (devoted both to Greek and Egyptian gods) that were introduced in the city during its development by the early Ptolemies. The most important temple

was the one devoted to Serapis, called the Serapeum. Other temples were also introduced during Roman conquest. Strabo (Geography, 17.10), who wrote during the early Roman empire mentions the city was full of temples, palaces and public places, and also mentions that ancient sacred places were abandoned.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

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Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

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Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

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Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: Strabo and other authors mention a temple where the tomb of Alexander was located, when Ptolemy I Soter brought the body from Babylon to the city and built a golden tomb for it. Strabo clarifies that at his time it was made of glass and that other Ptolemies also rested there (Geography, 17,1.8). It seems that the place became a landmark in the city, where many people visited, as it was constantly mentioned. Suetonius also mentions that when Octavian conquered the city, he dedicated honours to the tomb of Alexander and left many flowers (Augustus, 18).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Notes: The catacombs and necropolis in Alexandria are the most well preserved archaeological sites within the city and they mix Egyptian and Greek architectural styles. The main examples are the Chatby necropolis, Anfushi necropolis and Kom al-Chougafa.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: The better preserved temple in the city is the Serapeum, which was probably also the main temple. We know that the part of Alexandria where the palaces were located are now underwater, because of the level of the sea that has risen. Strabo mentions that the neighbourhood with palaces and important public spaces where a third of the city space, so probably many important temples were located in this area (Geography, 17.8). Arrian (also writing during Roman times, and after Strabo) also says that the city was full of temples, but affirms (clearly anachronically aimed to glorify Alexander) that the places where the temples should stand (to Greek gods and to the Egyptian Isis) were all determined by Alexander.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Altars:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: Strabo (Geography, 17.10) mentions that near the Serapeum there were many sacred places that were abandoned and replaced by new constructions at his time and that ancient buildings were neglected. He adds also that the city was full of public and sacred structures, and that the most beautiful was the gymnasium, where there were courts, forests and a sanctuary to the god Pan.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: We can mention the massive lighthouse of the Pharos, where there was also probably statues of gods.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– All public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– I don't know

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– All public spaces

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: An example is the Apis bull that was found in the Serapeum site during excavations at the end of the XIX century.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: Fragments of colossal statues of Ptolemaic kings and queens were found during the underwater findings.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Other features of iconography:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are pilgrimages present:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: In Egyptian religion the main belief was that after death, there was eternity. So if we consider the Egyptian portion of the city, they did consider that the afterlife was separated from the body. However, the physical body had to be preserved, so that the "spirit" had a place to come back if necessary. The sophisticated funerary religion of the Egyptian population influenced the constructions of the catacombs in the city.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– I don't know

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Supernatural beings care about sex:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
– I don't know
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
– I don't know
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: I will not consider the presence of a high god because of the mixed religious environment. But if we consider the Jewish community (some specialists estimate that they composed 1/3 of the city's inhabitants), Yahweh was the supreme and only god. If we consider the Greek and Egyptian community, they were the preferred gods, but not exclusivism. For example, Serapis had a kind of preference concerning the court, but it incorporated several other gods (like Hades, Pluto, Dionysus, Cerberus, Osiris) and was paired with Isis on many occasions. Its cult was also worshiped accompanied by secondary gods. So the picture is quite complex, depending on what community we look at.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Previously human spirits are present:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: The statues of deities were seen as their manifestation on earth and they were seen mainly on the occasions of festivities, that were part of the religious life of the city and were mostly established by the Ptolemaic courts, during roman period many of them are suspended.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Especially the kings and queens were seen as having divine attributes. To the Greeks they were semi-gods as they demonstrated charismatic and heroic military deeds, to the Egyptians they were associated to the Pharaonic position as a god on earth and also, sons of gods and its incarnation.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Notes: After the death of Ptolemy I Soter, Ptolemy II Philadelphus established a festivity in honour of his dead parents, where they became gods. When Ptolemy II married his sister Arsinoe II, they received dynastic honours as the theoi adelphoi ("the brother and sister gods"). Arsinoe II was also worshipped outside of Alexandria paired to Egyptian

gods. Alexander the great, was also honoured as a god and founder of the city. When crowned as pharaohs in Memphis, the Ptolemies also became the son of Ra and represented Horus to the Egyptians.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– No

Notes: There was no clear hierarchical organization of gods, only different levels of worships according to each social group.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: As for Egyptians, afterlife was eternity.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– Yes

Notes: If we consider the Greek Hades, it was seen as a space below. Concerning Egyptians, the underworld was also seen as a place where the crops would grow, the Osirian dominion. All these beliefs were probably also united in the cult to Serapis (Plutarch explains this syncretic process in his book *On Isis and Osiris*).

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– I don't know

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– I don't know

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Concerning Egyptian tradition, afterlife was based on the weighing of the heart, against the feather of MAAT, which represented justice and truth. So pleasures or punishments that were enjoyed in the afterlife was based on this belief. However, we do not know how this faith adapted to the Alexandrian atmosphere.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

— Yes

Notes: As Alexandria was a city with important harbours, that resulted in a busy commercial life not only inside Egypt, but as a crossroad to many routes, many gods were venerated concerning these maritime transactions. We know that Isis was really popular among navigators, and also Strabo mentions that there was a temple to Poseidon in the harbour area (*Geographica*, 17.8).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: One of the functions that Serapis acquired was that as a healing god, especially during the roman period and associated to Asclepius. There is a famous episode, narrated by Tacitus, that when the emperor Vespasian was as the city, he healed two people, inspired by Serapis (Histories, 4.81.4).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: If we consider the Egyptian population in the city.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: If we consider the Greco-Macedonian populace. The context is totally different for the Egyptians and Jews, which highly valued the afterlife.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
– No

↳ Other [specify]
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Mummification:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Secondary burial:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Personal effects:

– I don't know

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Yes [specify]: Amulets/ figurines in terracotta.

↳ Other grave goods:

– I don't know

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

Notes: We already mentioned the one in honour to Alexander, where the Ptolemies were latter also buried.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Catacombs.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Cooperation:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

Notes: This was particularly emphasized by roman governors, that tended to see the Alexandrians as always excessive and badly behaved (specially in public festivals).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: In Egyptian religion the main belief was that after death, there was eternity. So if we consider the Egyptian portion of the city, they did consider that the afterlife was separated from the body. However, the physical body had to be preserved, so that the “spirit” had a place to come back if necessary. The sophisticated funerary religion of the Egyptian population influenced the constructions of the catacombs in the city.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– I don't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: As for Egyptians, afterlife was eternity.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– Yes

Notes: If we consider the Greek Hades, it was seen as a space below. Concerning Egyptians, the underworld was also seen as a place where the crops would grow, the Osirian dominion. All these beliefs were probably also united in the cult to Serapis (Plutarch explains this syncretic process in his book *On Isis and Osiris*).

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– I don't know

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– I don't know

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Cremation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Mummification:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Interment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Cannibalism:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Feeding to animals:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Secondary burial:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Personal effects:

– I don't know

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

–Yes [specify]: Amulets/ figurines in terracotta.

↳ Other grave goods:

– I don't know

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

Notes: We already mentioned the one in honour to Alexander, where the Ptolemies were latter also buried.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Catacombs.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: I will not consider the presence of a high god because of the mixed religious environment. But if we consider the Jewish community (some specialists estimate that they composed 1/3 of the city's inhabitants), Yahweh was the supreme and only god. If we consider the Greek and Egyptian community, they were the preferred gods, but not exclusivism. For example, Serapis had a kind of preference concerning the court, but it incorporated several other gods (like Hades, Pluto, Dionysus, Cerberus, Osiris) and was paired with Isis on many occasions. Its cult was also worshiped accompanied by secondary gods. So the picture is quite complex, depending on what community we look at.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: The statues of deities were seen as their manifestation on earth and they were seen mainly on the occasions of festivities, that were part of the religious life of the city and were mostly established by the Ptolemaic courts, during roman period many of them are suspended.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Especially the kings and queens were seen as having divine attributes. To the Greeks they were semi-gods as they demonstrated charismatic and heroic military deeds, to the Egyptians they were associated to the Pharaonic position as a god on earth and also, sons of gods and its incarnation.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Notes: After the death of Ptolemy I Soter, Ptolemy II Philadelphus established a festivity in honour of his dead parents, where they became gods. When Ptolemy II married his sister Arsinoe II, they received dynastic honours as the theoi adelphoi ("the brother and sister gods"). Arsinoe II was also worshipped outside of Alexandria paired to Egyptian gods. Alexander the great, was also honoured as a god and founder of the city. When crowned as pharaohs in Memphis, the Ptolemies also became the son of Ra and represented Horus to the Egyptians.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Organized hierarchically:

– No

Notes: There was no clear hierarchical organization of gods, only different levels of worships according to each social group.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Concerning Egyptian tradition, afterlife was based on the weighing of the heart, against the feather of MAAT, which represented justice and truth. So pleasures or punishments that were enjoyed in the afterlife was based on this belief. However, we do not know how this faith adapted to the Alexandrian atmosphere.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

Notes: As Alexandria was a city with important harbours, that resulted in a busy commercial life not only inside Egypt, but as a crossroad to many routes, many gods were venerated concerning these maritime transactions. We know that Isis was really popular among navigators, and also Strabo mentions that there was a temple to Poseidon in the harbour area (Geographica, 17.8).

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
– Yes

Notes: One of the functions that Serapis acquired was that as a healing god, especially during the roman period and associated to Asclepius. There is a famous episode, narrated by Tacitus, that when the emperor Vespasian was at the city, he healed two people, inspired by Serapis (Histories, 4.81.4).

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Other [specify]
– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: If we consider the Egyptian population in the city.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: If we consider the Greco-Macedonian populace. The context is totally different for the Egyptians and Jews, which highly valued the afterlife.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Cooperation:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

Notes: This was particularly emphasized by roman governors, that tended to see the Alexandrians as always excessive and badly behaved (specially in public festivals).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: If we consider the Jewish community, the observation of the Sabbath was really important and also the law concerning pork consumption. Certainly these measures were rules that differentiated the group within the city, even if they were highly hellenized.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Circumcision:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Hair:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Dress:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Ornaments:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Other:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: If we consider the Jewish community, the observation of the Sabbath was really important and also the law concerning pork consumption. Certainly these measures were rules that differentiated the group within the city, even if they were highly hellenized.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

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Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

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– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

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"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

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Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

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– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Circumcision:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Hair:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Dress:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Ornaments:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Other:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Society and Institutions

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Notes: We can actually define two empires and two different periods, the Ptolemaic, based in Egypt and the court settled in Alexandria (but also including other possessions in the Mediterranean), and then its incorporation into a larger empire, the Roman.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– I don't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

— An empire

Notes: We can actually define two empires and two different periods, the Ptolemaic, based in Egypt and the court settled in Alexandria (but also including other possessions in the Mediterranean), and then its incorporation into a larger empire, the Roman.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– I don't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Bibliography

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